

THE METHODS FOR OBTAINING SAFE, NATURAL FOOD ADDITIVES FROM LOCAL AMARANTH VARIETIES

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Abstract. *The amaranth plant, recognized as the "plant of the 21st century" by the World Health Organization, is equally interested in both representatives of the agricultural sector and producers today. The rebirth of the amaranth plant has many problems that are relevant today, including the possibility of growing on degraded lands, its rich composition, the fact that it is cheap and easy to grow and process compared to other species of plants.*

Keywords: *amaranth, safe food, local varieties, mechanical processing, extraction*

Introduction. It is known that in conditions when global development and the development of science and technology are reflected in all spheres, one of the main tasks within the framework of food security of our country is the sustainable development of raw materials for local production and safe food products. [1, 3,4,5] Of course, such demand arises when using food additives, including dyes, in food technology, regardless of the consumer audience. Emphasizing in this regard the special place of food dyes, it cannot be denied that the share of synthetic dyes in the food industry is higher. [2,5,6,7] Today, one of the tasks facing specialists in the field of processing and storage of agricultural products is the creation, improvement and implementation of environmentally friendly technologies. For many, it is no secret that food dyes can be obtained from natural products available in our markets, including carrots, beets, pomegranates, etc.

Materials and methods. It is supported that when using natural food colors, attention should be paid to finding promising alternative raw materials of natural origin in terms of product composition, nutritional and biological value. [1,4,8,9] Food additives in the product are several hundred.

It can be seen that food additives are used to maintain the attractiveness of the product and attract consumers. In addition, it is possible to free the population from synthetic dyes with the "E" index and at the same time prevent some diseases that occur in the internal human body. [6,9,10,11,12,13] Introduction of the use of local and safe ingredients instead of synthetic substances allows extending the service life of the product several times, improving the color, taste and aroma, processing plant ingredients and eating it. It is necessary to develop a technology for obtaining food colors.

In addition, the cost of natural food additives, natural food colors obtained from local raw materials, is somewhat cheaper than the cost of synthetic dyes. This determines the cost-effectiveness and relevance of the work.

Moreover, the amaranth plant is processed using several different methods. These methods use different parts of the plant.

Results. As a result, it can be said that amaranth is an environmentally sustainable crop. It can grow in any climate and does not require much water for full development. In addition, amaranth has a short growth cycle, which allows for harvesting in a shorter time than other plant species. Amaranth is a plant with a rich history and potential for the future. Its nutritional value,

variety of uses and environmental sustainability make it an excellent choice for those seeking a healthy lifestyle. In the future, amaranth may become an even more important raw material base in the medical and industrial fields. [1,4,5,7,8] Developments and research in this area open up new possibilities for the use of amaranth in the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries.

Additionally, the processing of amaranth involves a number of chemical and physical processes and includes various stages. These processes are carried out to obtain the chemical composition of the plant, mainly biologically active substances, as well as food products.

1. Mechanical processing: the relevant parts of the amaranth plant (leaf, stem, grain, flowers) are separated by mechanical methods and crushed for preparation. In this process, physical changes occur in the plant substances. There are no significant changes in the chemical composition.

2. The extraction process is used to extract useful chemicals from amaranth, especially pigments and flavonoids (chemical compounds for medicinal purposes that act as antioxidants and protect the plant from external influences). [11,12,15,16,17] Extraction is carried out by the following methods:

Solvent extraction: coloring pigments and biologically active substances are separated from amaranth using organic or aqueous solutions.

Supercritical fluid extraction: using supercritical fluids such as carbon dioxide, highly efficient extraction is carried out without thermal damage [16,17,18]. In this case, physicochemical changes occur. The processes of dissolution and return of substances occur.

3. The fermentation process - is also involved in the processing of some amaranth products. In this process, microorganisms process carbohydrates and other organic substances in amaranth. During fermentation, various chemical changes occur. For example,

- the separation of sugars into organic acids;
- the production of amino acids and enzymes;

4. Extraction of pigments and synthesis of coloring agents - the plant contains natural pigments, in particular betalains. During their extraction, the following processes occur:

- the process of filtration and centrifugation, in which the pigments are separated in pure form by mechanical methods;
- in the process of chromatography, pigments and other biologically active substances are separated and analyzed by a chemical method;

5. Drying and storage processes: processed amaranth products are dried in the sun or using artificial drying agents. During the drying process, some substances in the plant's body evaporate. This, in turn, leads to physical changes.

Summary. All things are considered, it can be seen that amaranth is a plant that adapts to any conditions. The amaranth varieties "Lera", "Gelios", "Varoneisky", "Kharkovsky" are productive, with 0.5 kg of seeds per hectare you can get 2-5 tons of grain. These varieties were localized by scientists through introduction and became the basis for the creation of the varieties "Uzbekistan", "Marhamat", "Andizhan", "Ulugnor". In Uzbekistan, it has been noted that the plant sprouts well even on soil of average fertility, adapted to local climatic conditions.

Considering that the oil obtained from amaranth seeds is used in medicine, it is necessary to improve the technology for obtaining oil from its seeds and use resource-saving methods. Protein-rich grains and stems of plants can be used as feed for livestock, poultry and fisheries.

Amaranth, when grown as a secondary crop, has a good effect on soil fertility in agriculture as a green manure, which is a good idea for saline areas.

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